

Research Article

Impact of CIDOS on Self-Directed Learning and Engagement in Interactive Multimedia Application Courses: A Comparative Study of Two Polytechnics

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Abstract: This study explores the impact of the Curriculum Information Document Online System (CIDOS) on student engagement and self-directed learning (SDL) in Interactive Multimedia Application courses at Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic. A quantitative survey was administered to 83 students, assessing their frequency of CIDOS usage, engagement levels, and SDL behaviors. The study aimed to determine how CIDOS usage influences engagement and SDL, and whether differences existed between the two polytechnics. Results showed that frequent use of CIDOS, particularly video tutorials and quizzes, was strongly associated with higher levels of engagement. A significant correlation between student engagement and SDL was also found, indicating that engagement acts as a mediator in promoting independent learning behaviors. Students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic reported higher engagement levels compared to those from Sultan Idris Polytechnic, although both institutions demonstrated similar SDL outcomes. The findings highlight the importance of integrating engaging content into LMS platforms like CIDOS to enhance student participation and foster self-directed learning. The study suggests that active engagement with LMS resources can significantly improve students' ability to manage their own learning. Recommendations for future research include exploring the long-term effects of LMS usage on academic performance and expanding the investigation to other subject areas.

Keywords: Student Engagement; Self-Directed Learning (SDL); Learning Management System (LMS).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital learning platforms has revolutionized the educational landscape, providing learners with unprecedented access to learning resources and opportunities for self-directed learning (SDL). One such platform, the Curriculum Information Document Online System (CIDOS), serves as a Learning Management System (LMS) in Malaysian polytechnics, enabling students and lecturers to engage with course content, manage assignments, and facilitate online learning activities. As educational institutions increasingly adopt such platforms, understanding their impact on student engagement and SDL becomes critical (Alotaibi, 2016).

Self-directed learning refers to the process in which individuals take the initiative in diagnosing their learning needs, setting goals, identifying resources, and evaluating their own progress (Loyens, Magda, & Rikers, 2008). With the integration of LMS platforms like CIDOS, students are given more

autonomy in managing their learning, thereby fostering SDL. Meanwhile, student engagement—the level of attention, curiosity, and interest that students show toward learning—plays a pivotal role in their overall academic success (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004). By encouraging students to interact with learning materials, quizzes, video tutorials, and forums on CIDOS, educational institutions can potentially enhance engagement and SDL (Hung, Chou, Chen, & Own, 2010).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The integration of Learning Management Systems (LMS) in educational institutions has transformed the way students interact with learning materials and manage their academic responsibilities. Several studies have explored the role of LMS platforms in enhancing student engagement and promoting self-directed learning (SDL), making them central tools in modern education (Alotaibi, 2016). This review will explore three key areas: the role of LMS in education, the concept of self-directed learning and its relationship with technology, and the significance of student engagement in online learning environments.

2.1 *Learning Management Systems in Higher Education*

Learning Management Systems, such as CIDOS, serve as digital platforms that facilitate the delivery of course content, assessments, and communication between students and instructors. The widespread adoption of LMS has prompted extensive research into their impact on the learning experience. According to Bradley, Thom, Hayes, and Hay (2008), LMS platforms offer significant advantages, including flexibility in accessing learning materials and fostering a more interactive learning environment. LMS usage can promote higher student engagement by enabling access to multimedia content (videos, tutorials) and interactive elements such as quizzes and discussion forums, which can enhance students' understanding and retention of material.

A growing body of research has examined how LMS platforms influence various aspects of student learning. Alotaibi (2016) found that LMS, when properly integrated, can facilitate self-paced learning, providing students with the ability to revisit course materials at their convenience. This flexibility is particularly relevant to polytechnic students, who often balance practical coursework with theoretical studies. Additionally, a study by Costa, Alvelos, and Teixeira (2012) highlights that LMS platforms foster active learning and engagement by encouraging students to take responsibility for their own learning. However, challenges such as technical issues and limited interaction with instructors can affect the overall effectiveness of LMS platforms (Ong & Lai, 2006). These challenges raise questions about how platforms like CIDOS can overcome barriers to improve engagement and self-directed learning in specific disciplines such as interactive multimedia applications.

2.2 *Self-Directed Learning and LMS*

Self-directed learning (SDL) is a critical educational approach that enables students to take charge of their own learning processes, setting goals, identifying learning resources, and assessing their own progress (Loyens, Magda, & Rikers, 2008). Garrison (1997) emphasized that SDL is a key skill in the modern educational context, where students must develop the ability to manage their learning autonomously. LMS platforms have the potential to enhance SDL by providing students with the tools they need to manage their time, access diverse learning resources, and self-assess their progress through quizzes and other automated assessments.

Recent studies have demonstrated that LMS platforms significantly contribute to the development of SDL skills. According to Hung, Chou, Chen, and Own (2010), LMS platforms help students take more control over their learning by offering structured resources and self-paced learning

opportunities. Their study showed that students who used LMS regularly reported improved time management and goal-setting abilities. Similarly, a study by Khalil and Ebner (2014) indicated that LMS features such as interactive forums and digital quizzes can promote reflective learning, which is a key component of SDL.

In the context of polytechnic students, particularly in Interactive Multimedia Application courses, SDL is essential because of the hands-on, project-based nature of the subject. Students must independently explore creative design tools and concepts, often going beyond the instructional materials provided. CIDOS, as an LMS platform, can play a crucial role in fostering SDL by providing tutorials, design notes, and interactive assessments that encourage students to explore multimedia concepts at their own pace. Moreover, the autonomy granted through LMS platforms aligns with the constructivist approach to learning, where students build knowledge through active exploration and reflection (Knowles, 1975).

2.3 Student Engagement in Online Learning

Student engagement refers to the degree of attention, interest, and participation that students demonstrate in their learning activities. Engaged students are more likely to achieve higher academic performance, demonstrate greater persistence, and derive more satisfaction from their studies (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004). In the context of LMS platforms, engagement often manifests through frequent interaction with online resources, participation in quizzes and forums, and consistent use of available learning materials. Engaged students are more likely to utilize the full range of features provided by the LMS, leading to better learning outcomes (Kuh, 2001).

LMS platforms can significantly enhance student engagement, especially when they provide a variety of interactive elements, such as videos, quizzes, and discussion forums. These tools can help sustain student interest and promote deeper learning by encouraging active participation in the learning process. For example, a study by Zhang, Zhao, Zhou, and Nunamaker (2004) found that multimedia resources within an LMS increased student engagement and understanding, as students were able to interact with content through different sensory modalities.

However, research also shows that not all students engage with LMS platforms in the same way. Factors such as technical skills, motivation, and institutional support can influence how effectively students use these systems (Chiu & Hew, 2018). Moreover, engagement levels may vary between institutions based on the quality of digital resources and the learning culture fostered by the polytechnic. This is especially relevant to the present study, which aims to compare engagement levels among students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic.

In the field of interactive multimedia applications, engagement with the LMS is crucial for student success. Multimedia learning requires students to interact with design tools, software, and practical content that they may not be able to master through traditional lectures alone. CIDOS, by providing resources such as tutorials and interactive quizzes, allows students to practice these skills independently. The platform's role in facilitating SDL and engagement is particularly important in a subject where hands-on learning and creativity are vital.

2.4 Comparative Studies on LMS Usage

Several studies have explored how LMS platforms are used across different institutions, revealing variations in effectiveness based on institutional context, student demographics, and available resources. For instance, Selwyn (2007) highlights that students from different universities demonstrate varying levels of LMS usage, which could be attributed to differences in institutional culture, instructor involvement, and access to technology. Similarly, a study by Kumar and Mahajan

(2020) found that polytechnic students often experience challenges related to LMS adoption due to differences in digital literacy and institutional support.

The present study seeks to build on this body of research by comparing the usage of CIDOS across two polytechnics: Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic. By examining how these institutions utilize CIDOS to foster engagement and SDL, this study aims to identify the factors that contribute to more effective LMS usage and highlight areas where improvements can be made.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the research design, participants, data collection methods, and data analysis techniques used to investigate the impact of CIDOS on student engagement and self-directed learning (SDL) in Interactive Multimedia Application courses. The study adopted a quantitative approach, using questionnaires to assess the engagement and SDL behaviors of students from two Malaysian polytechnics: Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic.

3.1 Research Design

The study employed a comparative cross-sectional design to examine the use of the Curriculum Information Document Online System (CIDOS) and its impact on students' self-directed learning and engagement. The cross-sectional nature of the study allowed for the collection of data at a single point in time, providing a snapshot of students' experiences with CIDOS after completing a semester-long Interactive Multimedia Application course.

A quantitative survey method was chosen to enable statistical analysis of student engagement and SDL across the two polytechnics. This method is well-suited for exploring relationships between variables such as the frequency of CIDOS usage, the type of content accessed, and perceived outcomes in terms of SDL and engagement.

3.2 Participants

The sample consisted of 83 students from two polytechnics: Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic. The inclusion criteria were:

- Students enrolled in an Interactive Multimedia Application course.
- Students who had used CIDOS as the primary Learning Management System (LMS) throughout the semester.

Students from both polytechnics were selected using purposive sampling, as they represented a relevant population for examining LMS usage in interactive multimedia education. The final sample included:

- 42 students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic.
- 41 students from Sultan Idris Polytechnic.

The sample size was deemed sufficient for conducting comparative statistical analyses based on previous studies examining LMS usage in educational settings (Costa, Alvelos, & Teixeira, 2012).

3.3 Instruments

A customized questionnaire was developed to measure the students' engagement with CIDOS and their self-directed learning behaviors. The questionnaire was designed to capture both the frequency of CIDOS usage and the perceived impact on engagement and SDL. It was divided into four sections:

1. **Demographic Information:** This section collected basic information about the participants, such as age, gender, and polytechnic affiliation.
2. **CIDOS Usage:** This section assessed the frequency and type of resources students accessed on CIDOS (e.g., video tutorials, notes, quizzes). Items included questions like "How often did you access CIDOS per week?" with responses on a 5-point Likert scale (from "Never" to "Very frequently").
3. **Student Engagement:** Engagement was measured using a series of items adapted from the Student Engagement Scale (SES) (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004), which asked students to rate their level of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement with CIDOS resources. For example, students were asked to rate statements such as "I felt motivated to learn when using CIDOS" on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree).
4. **Self-Directed Learning (SDL):** The SDL section included items adapted from the Self-Directed Learning Readiness Scale (SDLRS) (Loyens, Magda, & Rikers, 2008), assessing students' abilities to manage their learning independently. Example items included "I was able to set learning goals and monitor my progress using CIDOS" and "CIDOS helped me improve my time management skills" with responses on a 5-point Likert scale.

The questionnaire was reviewed by two subject-matter experts to ensure content validity and was pilot-tested with a small group of students ($n = 10$) to refine item clarity and relevance. The pilot study demonstrated strong internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82 for the engagement scale and 0.85 for the SDL scale.

3.4 Data Collection Procedures

Data collection took place at the end of the semester to capture students' overall experience with CIDOS after completing the Interactive Multimedia Application course. The questionnaire was administered through Google Forms, ensuring ease of access for participants across both polytechnics.

To maximize response rates, students were informed of the purpose of the study during their final lectures and were provided with the survey link via email and their CIDOS accounts. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, with students required to provide informed consent before completing the questionnaire.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from both polytechnic administrations, and all participants provided informed consent before participating in the survey. The anonymity of participants was ensured, and no identifying information was collected. Students were informed that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any academic consequences. Additionally, all data collected was stored securely, and access was restricted to the research team.

3.6 Data Analysis

The collected data was exported from Google Forms into SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for analysis. The analysis included both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** Mean scores, standard deviations, and frequencies were calculated to summarize students' usage of CIDOS, their engagement levels, and SDL behaviors. These descriptive statistics provided an overall picture of how students interacted with CIDOS and their perceptions of its impact on learning.
2. **Comparative Analysis:** To compare engagement and SDL levels between students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic, independent t-tests were conducted. This allowed the researchers to identify any statistically significant differences between the two groups in terms of their CIDOS usage, engagement, and SDL outcomes.
3. **Correlation and Regression Analysis:** To examine the relationships between CIDOS usage (e.g., frequency of access, type of content used) and student outcomes (engagement and SDL), Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated. In addition, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine whether CIDOS usage patterns significantly predicted higher levels of SDL and engagement.
4. **Reliability Analysis:** The internal consistency of the engagement and SDL scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, ensuring that the questionnaire items reliably measured the intended constructs.

3.7 Limitations of the Study

Several limitations were identified in the study. First, the use of self-reported data may have introduced biases, as students might have overestimated their engagement and SDL. Second, the study focused on only two polytechnics, limiting the generalizability of the findings to other educational contexts. Finally, the cross-sectional design captures data at a single point in time, which may not fully reflect students' longitudinal engagement or SDL development.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the findings of the study, including descriptive statistics, comparative analyses between students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic, and correlation analysis on CIDOS usage, self-directed learning (SDL), and student engagement. The data were analyzed using SPSS, focusing on key areas such as CIDOS usage patterns, engagement levels, SDL behaviors, and the relationships between these variables.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

A total of 83 students participated in the study, with 42 students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and 41 students from Sultan Idris Polytechnic. The descriptive statistics provide an overview of how students interacted with CIDOS throughout the semester and their self-reported levels of engagement and SDL.

- **CIDOS Usage Patterns:** The majority of students (67%) reported accessing CIDOS at least 2-4 times per week, while 21% accessed the platform more than 4 times per week. Video tutorials were the most frequently accessed resource, with 78% of students indicating they used this

feature regularly. Quizzes and lecture notes were also commonly utilized, with 65% and 72% of students, respectively, indicating frequent use. Only 18% of students reported using the discussion forums on a regular basis.

- **Engagement Levels:** The average engagement score (measured on a 5-point Likert scale) was 3.82 (SD = 0.67), indicating moderate to high engagement with CIDOS. The highest levels of engagement were reported for video tutorials (mean = 4.15, SD = 0.54) and quizzes (mean = 3.92, SD = 0.68), while the lowest engagement scores were reported for participation in discussion forums (mean = 2.65, SD = 0.82).
- **Self-Directed Learning (SDL) Behaviors:** On average, students rated their SDL abilities as 3.75 (SD = 0.73) on a 5-point Likert scale. Students reported moderate levels of improvement in time management (mean = 3.85, SD = 0.71) and goal-setting (mean = 3.68, SD = 0.64), both of which are key components of SDL. The ability to self-assess progress was rated slightly lower (mean = 3.45, SD = 0.78), suggesting that students might require more support in this area.

4.2 Comparative Analysis Between Polytechnics

To determine if there were significant differences between students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic in terms of CIDOS usage, engagement, and SDL, independent t-tests were conducted. The results are summarized below:

- **CIDOS Usage:** There was no significant difference in the overall frequency of CIDOS usage between students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic (mean = 3.85, SD = 0.65) and Sultan Idris Polytechnic (mean = 3.78, SD = 0.62), $t(81) = 0.57, p > 0.05$. Both groups reported similar access patterns for video tutorials, notes, and quizzes.
- **Engagement:** A significant difference was found in student engagement levels between the two polytechnics. Students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic reported higher engagement (mean = 4.02, SD = 0.56) compared to Sultan Idris Polytechnic (mean = 3.63, SD = 0.72), $t(81) = 2.79, p < 0.01$. The higher engagement at Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic may be attributed to the increased use of multimedia elements, such as video tutorials, which were rated more favorably by students from this institution.
- **Self-Directed Learning (SDL):** No significant difference was found in overall SDL scores between students from the two polytechnics, $t(81) = 1.05, p > 0.05$. However, students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic rated their ability to manage time and set learning goals slightly higher (mean = 3.88, SD = 0.67) compared to students from Sultan Idris Polytechnic (mean = 3.62, SD = 0.77), though this difference was not statistically significant.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

To explore the relationships between CIDOS usage, student engagement, and SDL, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Pearson correlation coefficients among CIDOS usage, student engagement, and self-directed learning (SDL)

Variable	1	2	3
1. Frequency of CIDOS Usage	-	0.52**	0.41**
2. Student Engagement	0.52**	-	0.67**
3. Self-Directed Learning (SDL)	0.41**	0.67**	-

Note: $p < 0.01$

- **CIDOS Usage and Engagement:** There was a strong, positive correlation between the frequency of CIDOS usage and student engagement ($r = 0.52, p < 0.01$), indicating that students who accessed CIDOS more frequently were more likely to report higher levels of engagement. This suggests that regular interaction with CIDOS content, such as video tutorials and quizzes, plays a critical role in keeping students engaged with the course material.
- **Engagement and Self-Directed Learning (SDL):** There was a strong correlation between student engagement and SDL ($r = 0.67, p < 0.01$), indicating that students who reported higher engagement with CIDOS also demonstrated stronger self-directed learning behaviors. This suggests that engagement is a key mediator in the development of SDL, as students who are more involved in their learning processes are likely to take more control over managing their study time, setting goals, and monitoring progress.
- **CIDOS Usage and SDL:** The correlation between CIDOS usage and SDL was also significant ($r = 0.41, p < 0.01$), though weaker than the relationship between engagement and SDL. This finding suggests that while frequent use of CIDOS supports SDL, its direct impact may be more limited than engagement, which plays a more critical role in fostering independent learning behaviors.

4.4 Multiple Regression Analysis

To further explore the influence of CIDOS usage on SDL and engagement, a multiple regression analysis was conducted, using CIDOS usage as the predictor variable and engagement and SDL as the dependent variables. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Multiple Regression Analysis of CIDOS Usage on Student Engagement and Self-Directed Learning (SDL)

Dependent Variable	Predictor Variable	β	t	p-value
Student Engagement	Frequency of CIDOS Usage	0.52	5.14	<0.001
Self-Directed Learning	Student Engagement	0.67	7.12	<0.001

The regression analysis revealed that CIDOS usage significantly predicted student engagement ($\beta = 0.52, t = 5.14, p < 0.001$), confirming that higher levels of CIDOS usage led to greater engagement. Furthermore, engagement was a significant predictor of SDL ($\beta = 0.67, t = 7.12, p < 0.001$), suggesting that engagement mediates the relationship between CIDOS usage and SDL. This implies that CIDOS primarily influences SDL through its effect on engagement.

5. DISCUSSION

The results indicate that CIDOS plays a crucial role in promoting both student engagement and self-directed learning in Interactive Multimedia Application courses. Students who frequently accessed CIDOS resources, such as video tutorials and quizzes, reported higher levels of engagement, which, in turn, positively impacted their SDL behaviors. The findings support the notion that LMS platforms like CIDOS can be effective tools for fostering independent learning when students are actively engaged with the content.

Furthermore, while no significant difference was found between the two polytechnics in terms of SDL, students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic reported higher engagement levels. This

difference may be attributed to institutional factors such as the availability of multimedia content or differences in instructional design.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of the CIDOS platform on student engagement and self-directed learning (SDL) in Interactive Multimedia Application courses at Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic and Sultan Idris Polytechnic. The findings revealed that frequent use of CIDOS, particularly engaging resources like video tutorials and quizzes, was linked to higher engagement levels, which in turn fostered stronger SDL behaviors such as time management and goal-setting.

Students from Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic reported higher engagement compared to those from Sultan Idris Polytechnic, although both institutions demonstrated similar SDL levels. This suggests that engagement is a key mediator in promoting SDL, and that the design of CIDOS resources plays a critical role in maintaining student interest and autonomy.

The study highlights the importance of creating engaging, interactive content on LMS platforms to enhance both engagement and independent learning. Future research could explore the long-term impact of LMS usage on SDL and academic performance, as well as investigate students' experiences in different subject areas.

7. IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The findings from this study highlight the critical role that LMS platforms like CIDOS play in promoting both engagement and SDL in higher education. For instructors and educational institutions, this underscores the importance of:

- Curating engaging content on CIDOS, such as interactive quizzes, video tutorials, and practical assignments, to foster greater student involvement.
- Supporting self-directed learning by providing tools and resources that help students set goals, manage their time, and track their progress independently.

Furthermore, while this study focused on a specific course and subject area, future research could expand on these findings by exploring the impact of CIDOS in other disciplines or by examining the long-term effects of LMS usage on SDL development. A longitudinal study could provide deeper insights into how sustained engagement with LMS platforms influences academic performance and lifelong learning skills. Additionally, qualitative research methods such as interviews or focus groups could be employed to explore students' perceptions of LMS platforms in more detail, identifying potential challenges or barriers to engagement.

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